

A study on catalytic oxidative ring expansion and structural changes in 2-acetyl-2-methyl benzothiazoline involving some metal ions

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The Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of 2-acetyl-2-methylbenzothiazoline (AMBT) and 2-acetyl-3-methyl-4H-1,4-benzothiazine (AM4HBT) were synthesized. The ligand AMBT underwent structural changes prior to co-ordination with metal ion. It was observed that in presence of Cu^{II} and Fe^{II} , the AMBT oxidized to form AM4HBT *in situ* and then co-ordinated with the metal ions. On contrary, the ligand AMBT in presence of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} , converted itself to an open ring structure of Schiff base and then coordinated with the metal ions to form the corresponding complexes. To confirm these results, the complexes of Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with direct interaction from AM4HBT ligand were prepared.

Benzothiazoles and benzothiazines have been drawing much attention because of their vast potentiality as versatile co-ordinating agents, variety of biological activities and numerous applications in different fields of chemistry. The group N-C-S of benzothiazolines and benzothiazole hydrazones is of considerable chemotherapeutic interest and is responsible for pharmacological activity. A research on physiological activity of these compounds attributed their activity to their ability to chelate metal ions¹. It has been reported earlier that the condensation of 2-aminothiophenol with various carbonyl compounds yields benzothiazolines². The benzothiazolines in presence of metal ions undergo various structural changes^{3,4}. As the ligand is prone to undergo structural changes, the present investigation aimed to study the formation and characterization of complexes of 2-acetyl-2-methylbenzothiazoline (AMBT). To ascertain the formation of oxidative product, 2-acetyl-3-methyl-4H-1,4-benzothiazine (AM4HBT) from AMBT during complexation, the complexes were also prepared directly from AM4HBT. In the present communication we report synthesis and characterization of complexes formed from both AMBT (Fig. 1) and AM4HBT (Fig. 2).

AMBT

Fig. 1

AM4HBT

Fig. 2

Results and discussion

The complexes of 2-acetyl-2-methylbenzothiazoline (AMBT) and 2-acetyl-3-methyl-4H-1,4-benzothiazine (AM4HBT) involving Fe^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Cu^{II} were synthesized and characterized. In presence of Fe^{II} and Cu^{II} the AMBT undergoes oxidative ring expansion to form AM4HBT and then formation of corresponding complexes takes place. The complexes formed from AM4HBT directly are just same as those formed from AMBT. In contrast, with Co^{II} and Ni^{II} metal ions, the complexes resulted from AMBT are not the complexes of AM4HBT. Comparison of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes of AM4HBT and those of AMBT clearly reveals their separate identity. From the elemental analyses, 1 : 1 metal-to-ligand composition are evident in the complexes of AMBT and 1 : 2 in those of AM4HBT (Table 1). All the complexes are soluble in DMF and DMSO except

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of the ligands and their metal complexes*

Compd.	Colour	M.p. C°	Metal%	
			μ B.M.	Found (Calcd.)
AMBT	White	85-86	-	-
Co^{II} -AMBT	Brown	Dp	3.24	18.54 (18.48)
Ni^{II} -AMBT	Green	Dp	2.86	19.12 (18.53)
AM4HBT	Red	185-186	-	-
Fe^{II} -AM4HBT	Brown	Dp	-	12.73 (11.96)
Co^{II} -AM4HBT	Black	Dp	3.56	10.52 (12.47)
Ni^{II} -AM4HBT	Green	Dp	2.91	11.55 (12.51)
Cu^{II} -AM4HBT	Black	Dp	Zero	12.01 (13.35)

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N result.

Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of AMBT and were found to be non-electrolytes.

IR spectra : The IR spectrum of AMBT^{4,5} shows very sharp peak at 3332 cm⁻¹ attributable to νNH. The sharp peak observed at 1704 cm⁻¹ is due to νC=O. The IR data of AM4HBT indicates that the compound is an oxidized product of AMBT. A sharp peak at 3275 cm⁻¹ is due to νNH and a sharp peak with minimum intensity at 1603 cm⁻¹ is attributable to νC=O. The minimum intensity of νC=O peak is due to the existence of the ligand AM4HBT in resonance hybrid forms, which is also confirmed from X-ray data^{6,7}. Comparison of IR spectra of Cu^{II} and Fe^{II} of AMBT/AM4HBT reveals that the spectra are identical. This supports the conversion of AMBT to AM4HBT during complexation. The IR spectra of Fe^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes clearly reveals the absence of νNH and νC=O bands that are present in AM4HBT and a new broad band appeared in the region of 1600–1400 cm⁻¹ attributable to νC=N, indicating co-ordination through O and S atoms. The absence νNH and νC=O peaks and appearance of a new νC=N peak in the spectra of complexes can be attributed to loss of hydrogen atom from ring nitrogen of AM4HBT due to complex formation. However, the IR spectra of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes of AMBT show a broad band with shoulders in the region of 1650–1436 cm⁻¹, corresponding to quasi aromatic structure in the chelate ring involving C=C, C=N, C=O groups.

A broad trough in the region of 3000–3500 cm⁻¹ indicates presence of co-ordinated water in all the complexes of AMBT and AM4HBT. The nature of IR spectra of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes of AM4HBT are totally different from those of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of AMBT. The spectra of these complexes clearly reveal the presence of co-ordinated water and absence of νNH and νC=O peaks that are present in ligand spectrum.

TG analysis : Comparison of TGA of Fe^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of AMBT with the corresponding complexes of AM4HBT reveals that the thermograms are just superimposable. Thus TGA studies also supports *in situ* oxidative ring expansion of AMBT to form AM4HBT. The TGA of Co^{II}-AM4HBT complex shows weight loss of 44% up to 1000°. The Co^{II}-AMBT thermogram is totally different as compared to Co^{II}-AM4HBT. Similar results are observed in Ni^{II} system. Unlike Fe^{II} and Cu^{II} systems, the comparison of thermograms of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes with AMBT and AM4HBT reveals non-conversion of AMBT to AM4HBT *in situ* prior to co-ordination with the metal ions.

ESR spectrum : The ESR spectrum of Cu^{II}-AM4HBT complex shows two 'g' values indicating anisotropy. The g_{||}

value at 2.19 and g_⊥ value at 2.026 in Cu^{II}-AM4HBT clearly indicates anisotropy.

Magnetic moments : The magnetic measurements indicate the presence of unpaired electrons in Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes of AMBT and AM4HBT. The observed magnetic moment for Cu-AM4HBT complex is zero although the ESR spectrum of Cu^{II}-AM4HBT complex indicates presence of unpaired electron. This can be explained on the basis of antiparallel alignment of spin on adjacent Cu^{II} ions⁸.

Thus the co-ordination chemistry of AMBT is interesting as it undergoes two different structural changes during complexation. Based on above results, an open ring structure of the ligand in Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes and the oxidative ring expansion of AMBT to form AM4HBT in the presence of Cu^{II} and Fe^{II}, and then co-ordination of the oxidized product to form corresponding complexes is predicted. The structures of complexes of AMBT and AM4HBT, based on the above results are presented in Figs. 3 and 4.

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Experimental

The ligands AMBT and AM4HBT were prepared following the reported procedures^{6,9}. Their purity has been authenticated by TLC and by comparing their spectral data with literature. The spectral data are as follows : AMBT ν_{max} 3332 cm⁻¹ (NH), 1704 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ (CDCl₃; TMS) 1.8 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.15 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.9–3.2 (2H, q, CH₂), 5.0 (1H, s, NH), 6.55–7.18 (4H, m, arom CH)₃; AM4HBT ν_{max} 3275 cm⁻¹ (NH), 1603 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ (DMSO-*d*₆; TMS) 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.32 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.72–7.02 (4H, m, arom CH), 8.97 (1H, s, NH).

Synthesis of the complexes :

To a hot ethanol solution of AMBT/AM4HBT, was added aqueous MCl₂ (M^{II} = Co, Ni, and Cu)/MSO₄ (M^{II} = Fe) solution in 1 : 2 (M : L) molar ratios. In each case the mixture was refluxed for 12–16 h. The pH of the solution for complexation was maintained by adding few drops of dilute ethanolic ammonium hydroxide solution. The solid

complexes separated were filtered in hot condition, and then washed with hot ethanol, water and finally with petroleum ether and dried in vacuum.

The metal contents were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 2380 atomic absorption spectrophotometer and elemental analyses were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer 240C analyzer. Conductivity was measured on a Digisun DI 909 instrument at RT. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer and ESR spectra on a Joel SE 3X (X band) (LNT) instrument. The ^1H NMR spectra of the ligands were recorded on a Bruker WH 270 MHz NMR spectrometer. Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) of complexes were carried out on a Mettler Toledo Star System in the temperature range 0–1000°. Magnetic susceptibilities of the metal chelates were measured at RT on Faraday balance Model 7550.

References

1. Y. G. Yeow, F. Hoongkun, T. S. Beng and T. S. Guan, *Acta Cryst.*, 1991, **47**, 1347.
2. H. Chikashita, M. Miyazaki and K. Itoh, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans.*, 1987, 699.
3. T. Kawamoto and Y. Kushi, *Chem. Soc. Jpn. Chem. Lett.*, 1992, 893.
4. R. Cefalu, R. Bosco, F. Bonati, F. Maggio and R. Barbieri, *Zeitschrift fur anorganische and allgemeine chemie Band*, 1970, 376.
5. E. C. Alyea and A. Malek, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1975, **53**, 939.
6. F. Dibianca, E. Rivarola, A. L. Spek, H. A. Meinema and I. G. Noltes, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1973, **63**, 293.
7. G. Ferguson and B. Ruhl, *Cryst. Struct. Commun.*, 1982, **11**, 1033.
8. J. Lewis and R. G. Wilkins, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1960.
9. E. C. Alyea and A. Malek, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1985, **22**, 1325.